

A STUDY OF ELECTROLYTIC OXIDATION OF CHROMIC SULPHATE TO CHROMATE OR BICHROMATE. PART II.

By S. G. DIGHE

Comparison has been made between the potentials set up by the standard solution Cr_2SO_4 (containing $\text{CrO}_4^{=}$ 1.36 g. mol./litre) on electrodes made of the various alloys (Pb, Sb and Ag) with a view to ascertaining the role played by the anode in the process of electrolytic oxidation of chromic sulphate.

The series of experiments detailed in Part I have been carried out using platinum as electrode, which served very well to bring out the relative effects of change in composition of the solution, the electrode remaining constant. The electrode had the advantage of not complicating the process by itself acting chemically on any of the components, as platinum is known to be inert. At any rate, this electrode does not permanently change its chemical composition.

Assuming such an E.M.F. or redox potential obtained on platinum to be the standard value, comparison was made between the potential set up by a standard solution on electrodes made of various alloys. This process is likely to bring out the role played by the anode in the process of electrolytic oxidation of chromic sulphate solution.

The standard solution chosen for this purpose was made up of the stock chromium sulphate solution containing 0.68 g. mols. of Cr^{+++} per litre and the chromic acid solution containing 1.36 g. mols. of $\text{CrO}_4^{=}$ per litre and sulphuric acid containing 8 g. mols of H^+ ion per litre (*cf.* Part I).

The alloys chosen for making the anode had the following compositions :

Lead + 0.1% silver.

Lead + 3% antimony.

Lead + 3% antimony + 0.1% silver.

Lead + 6% antimony.

Lead + 6% antimony + 0.1% silver.

Lead-antimony anodes have been commonly used in accumulators. Addition of a small amount of silver had been found by Dornblatt and Fink (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1941, 79, 269) to have beneficial effect on the grid alloy for accumulators. Addition of a small percentage of silver to lead was advantageous when used as anodes for electrolysis of sodium chloride (Fink, *ibid.*, 1926, 129). It is also found advantageous in the composition of anodes used for electrolysis of zinc sulphate solutions (Koenig, McEwan and Larsen, *ibid.*, 1941, 79, 345).

It was therefore considered worthwhile investigating the behaviour of these alloys as anodes for oxidation of chromic sulphate to chromate. The study of these electrodes was two-fold namely determination of

(i) Redox potential set up on these electrodes as compared to that on bright platinum and platinised platinum by solutions of

(22) The efficiency of generation of chromate from chromic alum on these anodes.

The anodes when chemically untreated gave constantly changing values for redox potential. The anodes were therefore oxidised by keeping them in pickling solution of bichromate and sulphuric acid for a day before taking the potential readings. The readings thus obtained were fairly stable and are given below.

TABLE I
Redox potential with different electrodes.

(a) Test solution made up of :			
Propor. by vol. of stock soln.		Ionic comp. of the soln.	
H_2CrO_4	= 11.45 c.c.	$Cr_2O_7^{2-}$	= 0.155 g. mol./litre.
$Cr_2(SO_4)_3$	= 22.85	Cr^{+++}	= 0.310
H_2SO_4	= 4.25	H^+	= 1.00
made up to 50.00 c.c. with water.			
Electrode.	Readings of E' against Hg/Hg ₂ SO ₄ electrode.	Mean.	E_H (potential against hydrogen).
Bright platinum	+0.443	+0.443	1.085
	+0.443		
Platinised platinum	+0.435	+0.437	1.079
	+0.439		
Lead	-0.158	-0.158	0.484
	-0.158		
Pb+0.1% Ag	-0.045	-0.058	0.584
	-0.072		
Pb + 3% Sb	-0.138	-0.144	0.493
	-0.160		
Pb+3%Sb+0.1% Ag	+0.000	+0.005	0.647
	+0.009		
Pb + 6% Sb	-0.254	-0.254	0.388
	-0.254		
Pb + 6% Sb+0.1% Ag	-0.103	-0.103	0.539
	-0.103		
(b) Test solution made up of :			
Propor. by vol. of stock soln.		Ionic comp. of the test soln.	
$Na_2Cr_2O_7$	= 11.85 c.c.	$Cr_2O_7^{2-}$	= 0.16 g. mol./litre
$Cr_2(SO_4)_3$	} = 23.70	Cr^{+++}	= 0.32
Na_2SO_4		H^+	= 1.00
$24H_2O$			
H_2SO_4	= 6.25		
made up with water = 100.0 c.c.			
Electrode.	Readings of E' against Hg/Hg ₂ SO ₄ electrode.	Mean.	E_H (potential against hydrogen).
Bright platinum	+0.440	+0.440	1.082
	+0.440		
Platinised platinum	+0.433	+0.434	1.078
	+0.435		
Lead	-0.235	-0.236	0.406
	-0.237		

Electrode.	Readings of E against Hg/Hg_2SO_4 electrode.	Mean.	E_H (potential against hydrogen). +
Pb+0.1% Ag	-0.113	-0.117	0.525
	-0.121		
	-0.116		
Pb+3% Sb	-0.177	-0.178	0.464
	-0.179		
	-0.179		
Pb+3% Sb + 0.1% Ag	-0.029	-0.043	0.599
	-0.058		
Pb+6% Sb	-0.228	-0.226	0.416
	-0.226		
Pb+6% Sb+0.1% Ag	-0.183	-0.188	0.504
	-0.143		

It appears from the tables that potential set up with all these alloys is much more negative than with bright or platinised platinum. It will also be seen that the addition of silver to each of the alloys increases the redox potential.

For finding out the efficiency of generation of bichromate from chrome alum solution, a solution of chrome alum (sodium) containing 6% available $Na_2Cr_2O_7$ was used. This sodium chrome alum was made from stock chromium sulphate by adding the calculated quantity of Na_2SO_4 (anhydrous) and diluting with a strong solution of H_2SO_4 so that the composition of the solution was $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot NNa_2SO_4$, 6% (as available $Na_2Cr_2O_7$) and H_2SO_4 , 9.8 g/100 c.c.

The above liquor (15c.c.) was placed as anolyte in a porous pot of negligible resistance to passage of ions and having very low porosity for water and salt molecules. This porous pot was kept in a 350 c.c. beaker which contained 2N- H_2SO_4 solution in which was dipped a cylindrical lead sheet which formed the cathode.

FIG. 1.

Circuit enclosed above the dotted line is the generating circuit and below it is potentiometer circuit.

In the porous pot were immersed the anode rods to be tested, taking care that in each case the same area of anode was immersed, keeping the current density constant, as the same current was passed every time through the solution. The C.D. of 17.5 amps. per sq. ft. was kept. The voltage developed was noted as also the single electrode potential at the anode.

The determinations of the latter were made against Hg/Hg₂SO₄ electrode using 2N-H₂SO₄ bridge as equipment as in section I.

The electrodes were prepared from virgin metals in a vertical cylindrical mould and were used without any mechanical treatment of the surface, but they were chemically treated. As it is known that the unoxidised surface gives continuously changing readings of voltage, it was thought better to oxidise the surface of the anodes by keeping them in a strong solution of Na₂Cr₂O₇-H₂SO₄ mixture for a few days prior to use.

One hour before use they were oxidised electrolytically at the anode in a bichromate solution and after rinsing in water they were in each case immediately used in generation experiments. This pickling process ensures uniformity of oxide coating and is likely not to consume any portion of current in oxidising the surface to the detriment of the solution. The results must therefore be assumed to be free from all disturbing effects and differences in the behaviour must be assumed to be due to inherent differences in their composition. The recording voltmeter correct to 0.01 volt and ammeter reading upto 0.005 amp. were used. These readings were taken every hour and the experiment was over after the fourth reading during which period about 70% of available bichromate were generated. The generating beaker and the Hg₂SO₄ half cell were kept in a thermostat at 95°F. The thermo-regulator had a sensitiveness of ±0.5°F.

TABLE II

	Electrode-Pb.				Electrode-Pb+1%Ag.			
	Period in hours from start of generation.							
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Bichromate generation (in g.)	0.702	1.368	1.832	1.922	0.718	1.078	1.406	1.646
Voltage	2.90	2.95	2.95	2.95	2.95	2.87	2.99	2.88
Amperage.	0.415	0.40	0.425	0.425	0.425	0.392	0.396	0.415
% Current efficiency.	93.6	89.5	80.7	63.4	92.05	71.92	63.02	55.18
S. E. potential	1.363	1.377	1.404	1.418	1.315	1.329	1.365	1.316
	Electrode-Pb+3% Sb.				Electrode-Pb+3% Sb+0.1% Ag.			
Bichromate generation (in g.)	0.711	1.399	1.673	1.996	0.375	1.420	1.770	1.920
Voltage	2.92	2.96	2.94	2.95	2.80	2.80	2.81	2.84
Amperage	0.40	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.385	0.415	0.385
% Current efficiency	96.7	89.0	76.3	80.0	51.1	98.6	80.1	66.1
S. E. potential	1.338	1.411	1.416	1.423	1.233	1.288	1.327	1.380
	Electrode-Pb+6% Sb.				Electrode-Pb%+6% Sb+ 0.1% Ag.			
Bichromate generation (in g.)	0.780	1.945	1.675	1.891	0.826	1.231	1.693	1.677
Voltage	2.88	2.94	2.92	2.94	3.00	2.89	2.94	2.94
Amperage	0.40	0.40	0.415	0.425	0.47	0.35	0.40	0.42
% Current efficiency	99.5	91.62	75.01	62.8	96.0	81.2	75.0	58.6
S. E. potential	1.334	1.381	1.405	1.417	1.379	1.365		1.344

Summary of results.

Anode.	During generation of bi-bromate. Average voltage Terminal. Anodic.		Redox potential.	Over-voltage.	Current efficiency.
Pb	2.95	2.032	0.406 volts	1.626 volts	63%
Pb+3% Sb	2.94	2.039	0.464	1.575	68
Pb+6% Sb	2.92	2.026	0.416	1.612	63
Pb+0.1% Ag	2.93	1.973	0.525	1.448	55
Pb+0.1% Ag+ 3% Sb	2.81	1.949	0.599	1.350	66
Pb+0.1% Ag+ 6% Sb	2.94	2.005	0.501	1.501	58

From curves in Fig. 2, it would be seen that the alloys can be classified into two groups as

Group I.

Pb
Pb+3% Sb.
Pb+6% Sb.

Group II.

Pb+0.1% Ag.
Pb+3% Sb+0.1% Ag.
Pb+6% Sb+0.1% Ag.

Curves I and II show redox potential. Curves III and IV show anode potentials determined during bichromate generation experiments with each of these alloys as anode. These values are higher than the corresponding values in curves I & II. The difference must be due to oxygen overvoltage at these electrodes. For better comparison, values of efficiency of oxidation have been plotted on the same graph. (cf. Curves V and VI).

FIG. 2.

% of Sb in anode-alloy
Curves I, III & V refer to Pb-alloy and the rest to Pb + Ag alloy

FIG. 3.

The curves show that the investigated properties of alloys are not a near function of the antimony content of the alloy, 3% antimony content of the alloy being a turning point in the properties studied above.

Effect of addition of 0.1% Ag to Pb or Pb-Sb has been (i) to increase the redox value, (ii) to decrease the overvoltage, (iii) to decrease the current efficiency.

It seems (*cf.* Fig. 3) that for a particular group of alloys the smaller the overvoltage, the greater the efficiency of generation of bichromate. We see independent confirmation of this in the case of platinum anodes, the data for which are given below.

	Redox Pot.*	Oxygen overvoltage.**	Current efficiency***
Bright platinum	1.03 volts	1.47 volts	1%
Platinised platinum.	1.08	0.86	97

It is significant that bright platinum having almost the same redox potential value as but a higher overvoltage than that of platinised platinum.

Thus, these two anodes, which are chemically identical and have almost the same redox potential, offer convincing support for the conclusion drawn from the anodes of Pb, Ag and Sb that within a particular group of anodes the current efficiency is higher when the overvoltage is lower.

* Redox potential values are from author's data.

** Oxygen overvoltage figures from International tables (McGraw Hill).

*** C. E. figures are those of Gross and Hickling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 825).

This conclusion seems to be in opposition to the generally accepted principle "that higher overvoltage conduces to higher efficiency of oxidation". This apparent contradiction, however, gives us an insight into the part played by the anode. The above accepted principle would be true for insoluble anodes where the equilibrium is set up between the two opposing tendencies of the reaction in solution, *via* the electrode, which acts as a conductor and takes no part in the chemical reaction. Thus, the E.M.F. set up on an insoluble electrode is a function of the energy change in solution only.

The lead alloy electrodes on the other hand do not seem to be truly insoluble. This is borne out by the fact that while redox potential is quickly set up on bright platinum, which is insoluble, the redox potential in the case of lead alloy electrode attains a steady value only after a lapse of some hours. The E.M.F. set up on electrodes of lead alloys seems to be a resultant of the energy change due to the normal reaction in solution and the energy change due to reactions between the electrodes and the solutions.

It is significant that redox potential on platinised platinum which is chemically identical with bright platinum is also +1.08 volts. The redox potential value, therefore, seems to be governed by the chemical nature of the anodes; whereas, the overvoltage values, as generally accepted, are determined to a large extent by the physical nature of the surface, as is evidenced by the large difference of overvoltage shown by bright platinum and platinised platinum.

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ASSAY DEPARTMENT,
HIS MAJESTY'S MINT,
BOMBAY.

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